

GNSS Reflectometry for Soil Moisture Retrieval: Methods and Approaches - A Review

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ABSTRACT

Soil moisture, an essential component of the hydrological studies, plays a pivotal role in agricultural irrigation, weather systems, and global water cycle dynamics. Conventional methods of assessing soil moisture, such as in situ measurements, face limitations in coverage, scalability, and their ability to contribute to disaster prevention and insights into the water cycle. Microwave remote sensing satellites offer advantages like sensitivity, cloud penetration, and independence from solar energy but fall short in providing high temporal resolution. New advancements in Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) have expanded their utility beyond positioning and navigation with the introduction of GNSS Reflectometry (GNSS-R), a technique for estimating soil moisture. This system can function as an altimeter or scatterometer, estimating land or ocean surface characteristics like height, roughness, and dielectric properties. One can estimate geophysical parameters such as snow depth, sea ice, winds, water level, vegetation, and soil moisture using a variety of techniques. The paper describes retrieval strategies that focus on the benefits and drawbacks of both remote sensing and in situ measurement techniques. It focuses on the underlying concepts of GNSS technology, describing how it detects reflected signals on the surface of the earth to estimate soil moisture. It emphasizes GNSS-R benefits of GNSS-R, including low cost, global coverage, all-weather capability, and high spatial and temporal resolutions. In this paper, the noteworthy advancements in GNSS-R soil moisture monitoring are highlighted and investigates how GNSS-R may provide insightful information about soil moisture dynamics. By using cutting-edge remote sensing techniques, it supports a range of applications and tackles environmental challenges.

Keywords: Soil moisture, microwave remote sensing, GNSS-R.

INTRODUCTION

The water that is held in the soil and is influenced by various factors such as temperature, precipitation, and soil properties, is known as soil moisture. An understanding of soil moisture is essential for agricultural irrigation. Additionally, it influences the percentage of runoff, evaporation, and percolation of rainfall on land. Because of its impact on the global water cycle, knowing the moisture content of the soil near the surface is helpful for hydrological research, climate studies, crop management, and predicting possible flood and drought risks. Monitoring major surface water resources in situ is generally not possible due to the difficulties connected with the expensive nature of monitoring equipment and the requirement for numerous observation stations via in situ

methods. As a result, many weather prediction models have a substantial missing parameter due to a lack of data. Surface emission and signal reflection have the ability to measure soil moisture because they have an effect on the soil medium's relative permittivity or dielectric constant. As a result, substantial research on ground-based, aerial, and space-based remote sensing technologies such as radiometers and radars, along with emerging techniques such as LiDAR-based observations [1], to analyse soil moisture has been done, principally based on the soil's dielectric constant.

The methods for detecting soil moisture that are frequently used are wet weight, soil humid meter, or electric resistance, etc. are quite precise, but they don't go far enough in terms of application to forecast models for disaster prevention or even a deeper comprehension of the water cycle. L-band frequencies are most effective at measuring soil moisture in the upper 0–2 cm of the surface, according to research by O'Neill in 1982 [2] and Wang in 1980 [3]. This is explained by improved penetration through vegetation and less interference from the atmosphere. However, the capacity to monitor soil dielectric characteristics with increased sensitivity and capability has been made possible by microwave remote sensing satellites [4, 5]. This technique has a number of advantages, including the capacity to work without solar energy, pass through clouds, and identify changes with increased sensitivity. Satellites that use microwave remote sensing are able to measure the moisture content of the

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surface soil, which is useful not only for monitoring geological hazards but also for socioeconomic study. Over the last few decades, microwave sensors, both passive and active, have become popular in for soil moisture monitoring. The impact of soil dielectric properties on microwave signals is a significant advantage of microwave remote sensing. As a result, the majority of retrieval techniques employ dielectric mixing models to recover soil moisture [6].

Through the detection of reflected signals on the surface of the Earth, GNSS have demonstrated their efficacy as an emerging observational approach in recent times. GNSS are a network of satellites that orbit the Earth and provide position, navigation, and timing (PNT) data to customers worldwide, including civilian and strategic users. GNSS has effectively expanded its ability to monitor a wide range of domains, including the atmosphere, ionosphere, oceans, land surfaces, and cryosphere, by introducing novel detection technologies [7, 8]. The only globally operating GNSS as of 2014 are the Global Positioning System (GPS) of the United States and the GLONASS of Russia. The

Beidou Navigation System (BDS), a GNSS that China has also developed its own GNSS intending to provide worldwide coverage. Galileo, a GNSS developed by the European Union, Japanese Aerospace Exploration Agency launched QZSS, and ISRO of India developed IRNSS also known as NavIC in 2013 [9]. Comparison of these systems is shown in Table 1. A few benefits of GNSS technology are its low cost, worldwide coverage, all-weather measuring capacity, revisiting time, and high temporal and spatial resolution near-real-time monitoring. In geodetic applications, particularly GNSS reflectometry (GNSS-R), it can be used more frequently [10]. Since then, the GNSS-R field has been the target of numerous studies. The launch of these satellites in 2014 marked a significant milestone in the field, enabling researchers to explore the full potential of GNSS-R for various environmental and geophysical studies. It has been used in ocean altimetry [11] and scatterometry, with applications in geodetic studies, climate change measurements, and ecological concerns like water level [12, 13], snow depth [14, 15], vegetation growth [16, 17], and soil moisture [18, 19].

Table 1. Comparison of GNSS Systems

System	NAVSTAR GPS	GLONASS	Galileo	BeiDou	IRNSS	QZSS
Country Launch	US 1978	EU 1982	Russia 2005	China 2000	India 2013	Japan 2010
Coverage Coding	Global CDMA	Global FDMA & CDMA	Global CDMA	Global CDMA	Regional CDMA	Regional CDMA
Satellites Height	32 20,180km	24 19,130km	25 23,222km	44 36000km & 20,150 km	7 35,786km	5 32,600km
Revolution	12h 52min	14h 5min	11h 58min	11h 16min	23h 56min	23h 56min
Accuracy (Global)	3m Horizontal 5m Vertical	5-10m Horizontal 15m Vertical	1m	20m Horizontal 30m Vertical	20m	1-3 m
Reference system	WGS 84	PZ-90	GTRF	CGCS2000	WGS 84	JGS
Band Frequency (GHz)	L1: 1.563–1.587 L2: 1.215– 1.2396 L5: 1.164– 1.189	G1: 1.593– 1.610 G2: 1.237– 1.254 G3: 1.189– 1.214	E1:1.575 E5a: 1.176 E5b:1.207 E6: 1.278	B1:1.561 B2: 1.207 B3: 1.268	L5: 1.164- 1.188 S: 2.484- 2.500	L1: 1.575 L2: 1.227 L5: 1.176 L6: 1.278
Status	Operational	Operational	Operational	Operational	Operational	Operational

A. EVOLUTION OF GNSS-R APPLICATIONS

Because of its potential applications in a variety of fields, GNSS-R technology has attracted a lot of attention recently, such as oceanography, agriculture, and climate monitoring. By utilizing the signals from existing GNSS satellites, GNSS-R offers a cost-effective solution for collecting valuable data about the Earth's surface without the need for dedicated sensors or infrastructure. GNSS bistatic radar utilizes the signals from GNSS to perform radar measurements. Hall and Cordey first introduced this

idea when researching multi-static scatterometry, which they used to determine the wind direction above the ocean. Martin-Neira [11] developed the Ocean surface elevations can be estimated through altimetry by using reflected GPS signals, as recommended by the Passive Reflectometry and Interferometry System (PARIS).

Katzberg and Garrison [20] proposed the use of ocean-reflected signals from Low Earth Orbit satellites to measure ionospheric delay, aiming to improve single-frequency altimeter performance and enhance model

accuracy by integrating GPS bounce signals. In order to measure sea surface roughness, Garrison et al. [21] carried out airplane tests using a modified GPS receiver and a left-hand circularly polarized (LHCP) antenna that was positioned nadir. They achieved this by monitoring for GPS signal reflections from water surfaces throughout a range of sea conditions. Kavak 1998 [22] used ground based GPS receiver data to examine impact of ground specular reflections on L-band satellite communications and introduced a reliable method to measure permittivity. Komjathy et al. [23] presented GPS's versatility in oceanography, extending beyond navigation to study sea surface roughness, wind speed variations, wave height, salinity, and ionospheric Total Electron Content, showcasing its potential for comprehensive oceanic research.

Zavorotny and Voronovich [24] built a strong theoretical framework based on the Kirchhoff approximation and a bistatic radar equation. This model described the power of GPS signals scattered concerning various geometrical and environmental parameters, with particular focus on wind conditions for determining sea surface wind speed. They observed that the GPS signal, commonly utilized for bistatic ocean scatterometry and wind retrieval purposes, could additionally be employed for soil moisture detection, given that soil reflectivity at GPS frequencies is responsive to variations in moisture content [25]. A GPS system was added to a Hurricane Hunter research aircraft owned by NOAA in October 2000. The objective was to record surface signals during Hurricane Michael along the Florida coast [26]. In [27] Treuhaft et al. demonstrated accurate altimetry over a lake, achieving estimates of surface height with a precision of two cm in just one second, which is a noteworthy accomplishment in high-precision altitude measurement.

The first space borne mission of GNSS-R was Survey Satellite Technology Ltd (SSTL) UK-DMC or BNSCSAT-1 (Disaster Monitoring Constellation), launched on September 27, 2003, marked the pioneering satellite mission specifically associated with GNSS-R. This mission aimed to sense ocean roughness until its retirement in 2011 [28]. UK TechDemoSat-1, launched on 8 July 2014, includes the Space GNSS Receiver (SGR-RESI) developed by SSTL for sea state monitoring [29]. The University of Michigan and Southwest Research Institute's CYGNSS space-borne mission, funded by NASA, launched eight microsattellites for hurricane forecasting on December 15, 2016 [30]. WNISAT-1, a Japanese Arctic Sea monitoring mission, launched on July 14, 2017, focuses on optical observations of diverse environmental elements such as sea ice, typhoons, volcanic ash clouds, among others. Delay-Doppler maps and GNSS signal capture are the responsibilities of the GNSS-R receiver that is part of the WNISAT-IR payload [31]. China's first GNSS-R constellation was launched on June 5, 2019, with the BuFeng-1 A/B twin satellites. 2021 onwards FengYun-3 (FY-3) series satellites are providing soil moisture. This mission is specifically designed to conducting in-orbit evaluations of GNSS-R, specifically targeting the

monitoring the sea surface wind velocity field, notably during typhoons [32]. The third spacecraft built by SSTL (Surrey Satellite Technology Limited) especially for GNSS-R research was launched on July 5, 2019, with the DoT-1 (Demonstration of Technology-1) satellite. Evaluating cutting-edge electronics, in particular antenna technology, with potential uses in future space-borne technologies is the primary goal of the DoT-1 satellite [33].

This paper discusses soil moisture retrieval methods from GNSS-R. In the next section, structure of GNSS signal is explained. In section 3, Basic principles of GNSS-R are discussed. In section 4, in situ and microwave remote sensing approaches techniques are discussed. GNSS techniques and GNSS-R soil moisture retrieval approaches are discussed in section 5. A detailed summary and discussion is provided in section 6. Finally, Conclusion is given in section 7.

II. STRUCTURE OF GNSS SIGNALS

Being the first GNSS in use, the GPS was created to make it possible for several transmitters to share a single frequency band. Because of multipath and jamming, it was intended to operate at a low power spectral density to avoid interfering with other microwave systems. Spread spectrum techniques are used to achieve these goals. In particular, the pseudo-random rectangular code considerably higher in frequency than the data is combined with the navigation signal to increase its bandwidth. With auto-correlation and cross-correlation characteristics, pseudo-random noise (PRN) performs as a spreading sequence and offers precise production and regeneration [34]. Each GPS satellite employs a unique PRN code, facilitating discrimination between transmitters, and providing range estimates for user positioning through triangulation.

Three components make up a GNSS signal, as shown in Fig. 1: a spreading waveform, a data waveform, and an RF carrier. A series of 20-millisecond rectangular pulses at 50 Hz describe the data waveform, which is derived from binary 50-bits-per-second navigation data, but the RF carrier is a sinusoidal wave. The spreading waveform is a series of codes created by applying a deterministic pseudorandom noise coding. A chip is the smallest interval of time between transitions, and the clock rate of the binary PRN code is represented by the chipping rate [35].

The Coarse Acquisition (C/A) codes, designed for open-access civil service, exhibit a 1 ms period and 1023 chips length. These codes boast high autocorrelation peaks for clear satellite identification and low cross-correlation peaks to prevent interference among signals from different satellites. Specifically, a code known as P is used for secure military messages. Compared to the C/A code (10.23 MHz), its chipping rate is ten times faster, and its coding period is one week for each satellite (total 266 days). The observable pseudo-range accuracy improves tenfold with this arrangement. There are data fields inside navigation frames that need to be accessed in order to get the P code. An encrypted version known as P(Y) can also

be enabled for more security. As shown in eq. 1, the C/A and P codes onto the L1 carrier are [36]:

$$S_1(t) = \sqrt{2 \cdot P_{C/A_1}} D(t) \cdot CA(t) \cdot \cos(w_1 \cdot t + \phi_1) + \sqrt{2 \cdot P_{P_1}} D(t) \cdot P(t) \cdot \sin(w_1 \cdot t + \phi_1) \quad (1)$$

GPS satellite's signal is denoted by the phrase $S_1(t)$, At L1, the transmitted power for C/A signal is denoted by P_{C/A_1} , whereas the power for P code signal is denoted by P_{P_1} .

Fig. 1. GNSS Signal Structure

III. BASIC PRINCIPLES OF GNSS-R

GNSS-R is a bistatic radar technique that uses scattered signals off the Earth's surface to estimate geo-physical parameters. The constant reliability and global availability of GNSS signals make them highly suitable for remote sensing applications, which has resulted in increasing interest within the scientific community. The number of navigation signals that interact with the Earth's surface and travel through the atmosphere increases as GNSS satellites are launched into orbit, enhancing the temporal and spatial coverage of a range of natural events. GNSS-R uses a single receiver to retrieve geo-physical parameters from multiple GNSS satellites, potentially obtaining signals from more than 20 emitters simultaneously. This may lead to a reduction in noise when estimating geo-physical parameters or an increase in the instrument's swath.

GNSS-R is a form of bistatic radar, where the transmitter and receiver are separated by a considerable distance. The bistatic radar equation (eq. 2) governs the power observed by the receiver, taking into account various factors such as transmitted power, antenna gains, and scattering coefficient [37].

$$P_{pq}^r = \frac{P_t \lambda^2}{(4\pi)^3} \int \frac{G_t G_r}{R_t^2 R_r^2} \sigma_{pq}^0 dA \quad (2)$$

Where, P_t for the transmitter's power and $G_t G_r$ are antenna gain patterns. Furthermore, the receiver gain pattern is denoted by G_r , and the separations between the specular point, the transmitter, and the receiver are

indicated by R_t and R_r respectively, σ_{pq}^0 is the scattering coefficient. An object's ability to reemit incident energy in a particular direction is indicated by its scattering coefficient. It is crucial for understanding how signals interact with the Earth's surface and are reflected back to the receiver. It can be written as: Satellite signals, such as those from GPS, are utilized in GNSS-R. These signals are scattered off the Earth's surface, and detecting their reflections allows for the retrieval of geophysical parameters of the scattering surface. When GNSS-R is used, a single receiver that operates in a multi-static configuration simultaneously receives direct and reflected signals from several GNSS satellites.

A. SCATTERING GEOMETRY

When a wave strikes a flat surface at the specular point, all of the surface points reflect in phase in the direction of the receiver which is known as spatial reflection. There is a quadratic phase change throughout the illuminated region as a result of the electromagnetic field at the transmitter behaving more like a spherical wave. Within the first Fresnel zone, the phase stays close to the specular point and includes points where the path difference is less than half the wavelength, adding positively to the scattered field [38]. The received power increases when surface roughness increases because it permits distant points from the nominal specular point to reroute incident waves towards the receiver. This active scattering area is called the glistening zone, which causes scattering called as diffuse, or incoherent component, is the power that is distributed randomly in all directions.

The calculation of the distance from any surface point to the specular point allows for the establishment of iso-range lines, which are depicted as ellipses on the surface, indicating areas with consistent delay from the specular point. Variations in the geometry among the transmitter, surface, and receiver lead to Doppler shifts observed at locations within the glistening zone. These iso-delay and iso-Doppler lines are illustrated as ellipses and hyperbolas, respectively as described in Fig. 2 with the specular point at the origin and transmitter and receiver positions defined by vectors. The geometry of the transmitter and receiver determines the dimensions and form of the iso-Delay and iso-Doppler lines. For instance, the height of the receiver affects the first chip zone's area, whereas the transmitter and receiver's velocities determine the Doppler shift's magnitude [39]. The semi-major and semi-minor axes of the iso-range ellipses are derived from eq. 3 [20]:

$$a = \frac{\sqrt{2\delta H \cos\theta}}{\cos^2(\theta)} \quad b = \frac{\sqrt{2\delta H \cos\theta}}{\cos(\theta)} \quad (3)$$

GNSS-R creates the Delay-Doppler map (DDM) by using signals from GNSS satellites that are reflected off the surface of the Earth. This technology uses incoming signals to cross-correlate with a GNSS satellite's PRN code, similar to match-filter signal processing in conventional radar systems. The resulting DDM provides insightful

information about surface properties and is useful for a range of remote sensing applications, including tracking soil moisture content, spotting surface deformations, and examining vegetation development patterns. This technology also helps with scientific studies on wave heights and ocean currents, which enhances marine navigation and improves weather forecasts.

Fig. 2. Iso-delay ellipses (blue) and Iso-Doppler lines (red)

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The GNSS-R bistatic radar system uses GNSS signals to illuminate the Earth's surface while also capturing weak dispersed signals using bistatic radar. Receiving these signals is difficult because to their intrinsic weakness, hence signals in the first Fresnel zone, a small angular zone surrounding the specular direction, are the focus of GNSS bistatic radars. Surface scattering mechanisms determine how particles interact with the Earth's surface. Spatially coherent reflection, or specular reflection, preserves coherence when the Earth's surface is smooth and level. However, diffuse scattering occurs when the heights of rough surfaces are greater than the signal's wavelength, which causes the specular component to vanish. This phenomenon is especially noticeable when waves are created by wind on the sea's surface. The GNSS-R bistatic radar equation provides a mathematical framework for understanding scattering and retrieving information from the Earth's surface. This equation permits the creation of the DDM, which provides information about scattering characteristics and surface qualities. The equation can be expressed as [24]:

$$\langle |Y(\tau, f)|^2 \rangle = \frac{T_i^2 P_t G_t \lambda^2}{4\pi^3} \iint_A \frac{G_r}{R_t^2 R_r^2} \chi^2(\tau, f) \sigma_0 dS \quad (4)$$

Here, T_i stands for coherent integration time, and, $P_t G_t$ for the transmitter's power and gain pattern. Furthermore, the receiver gain pattern is denoted by G_r , and the separations between the specular point, the transmitter, and the receiver are indicated by R_t and R_r respectively, The Woodward ambiguity function (WAF) is represented by the symbol χ^2 , while the rough surface's normalized bistatic radar cross section (BRCS) is denoted as σ_0 . The intensity of the scattered signal moving toward the receiver's antenna from a specific spot on the uneven surface is represented by σ_0 . This term is given by the following equation (eq. 5) given by Kirchoff approximation [36]:

$$\sigma_0 = \pi |\mathfrak{R}|^2 (q/q_z)^4 P(-q_{\perp}/q_z) \quad (5)$$

The complex Fresnel coefficient R , which is determined by the incidence angle, the dielectric constant of the reflecting medium, and the signal's polarization state, determines the value of σ_0 . The bistatic radar equation does have some restrictions, too. When there is fully diffuse surface scattering, it performs best because the coherent specular component is either completely absent or negligible. However, in other cases, the coherent component of the scattering phenomenon might be detectable and perhaps difficult. This is seen in forward scattering from calm oceans, lakes, generally level terrain, or sea ice with low surface roughness. Coherent aspect is important, especially on smooth and flat surfaces, and measured by direct signal cross-correlation power, Fresnel coefficient (R), and a surface roughness dependent term, represented by eq. 6.

$$\langle |Y(\tau, f)|^2 \rangle = |Y(\tau, f)|^2 |\mathfrak{R}| e^{\frac{-8\pi^2 \sigma_h^2 \cos^2 \theta}{\lambda^2}} \quad (6)$$

The DDM will exhibit a unique peak as a result of this expression, which is centred on the delay and Doppler offset related with the specular point on the surface. Surface roughness and the upper layer of the medium's dielectric permittivity are the primary factors that impact the BRCS, which introduces the surface's influence on the bistatic radar equation. Signal quality is improved by GNSS bistatic radar by adding a coherent reflection term that targets the delay and frequency offset related to the expected specular spot on Earth's surface. This feature addresses the need for incoherent integration during observation time, decreasing residual noise that could affect the accuracy of obtaining the optimum average waveform.

B. DDM AND SPATIAL RESOLUTION

Combining the WAF and BRCS inside the antenna footprint yields the DDM. Within the Delay-Doppler domain, the scattering coefficient is represented by this

map, with values close to unity within the Doppler zone and nearly zero outside of it. In the physical world, certain surface features produce scattered signals that, when they reach the receiver, have the same traveling route length. According to certain surface characteristics, the scattered signal also exhibits the same Doppler shift. From a geometric standpoint, the intersection of the Earth's surface and the equal-delay ellipsoid produced by GNSS signals defines the borders of the annulus zones. These iso-range lines are ellipses. The iso-Doppler lines can be derived from the given eq. 7 described in [40]:

$$f_D(x, y) = \frac{1}{\lambda} (\vec{V}_T \cdot \hat{k}_i(x, y) - \vec{V}_R \cdot \hat{k}_s(x, y)) \quad (7)$$

where \vec{V}_T and \vec{V}_R are transmitter and receiver velocities with respect to earth's surface, \hat{k}_i and \hat{k}_s are incident and scattering direction unitary vectors. A one-dimensional waveform that represents a portion of a DDM along the time delay that can be detected by some GNSS reflection receivers. The waveform has a fixed frequency offset that is meant to counteract the Doppler shift associated with the specular point. The core elliptic annulus zone is responsible for producing the first part of this waveform, which reaches the peak value, as it grows from zero to its maximum. The peak of reflected power varies in response to fluctuations in sea surface roughness, which modifies the DDM's form. When considering bistatic scattering, the relationship between observed peak power and wind speed is inversely correlated with backscattering geometry. A strong forward reflection produces an extremely strong received signal at low wind speeds. On the other hand, peak power decreases with increasing wind speed.

The geometry and the type of surface scattering both influence a bistatic GNSS-R radar's spatial resolution. The first Fresnel zone is the only place where the spatial resolution is found when the Rayleigh value is less than one, which indicates predominant specular reflection. For airplanes flying between 5 and 10 km, this zone extends across several tens of meters. However, the zone widens to hundreds of meters around 600 km satellite altitudes. However, natural surfaces tend to exhibit more diffuse, quasi-specular scattering, which leads to bigger sparkling zones. By working as a spatial filter, the WAF transforms the scattered signal into a DDM, in which pixels control the spatial resolution. Longer time gaps may cause equi-range zones to condense further, possibly leading to fewer pixels. However, issues like noise, ambiguity, and poor power can affect the spatial resolution.

The largest surface pixels are those that contribute most to the power of the DDM, particularly around the notional specular point. The first zone around specular point yields better spatial resolution in this setup. This ground pixel's size depends on variables such receiver altitude, angle of incidence, and code chip length. For example, when using C/A coding, a 1-ms coherent integration time, and a 600 km receiver altitude, the predicted pixel size is between 20 and 30 km. Incoherent accumulation over time, influenced

by the motion of the receiver and footprint, can affect the overall spatial resolution, depending on integration times and other parameters.

IV. SOIL MOISTURE ESTIMATION

Soil moisture measuring systems work at different scales and include both direct and indirect methods. Direct methods involve drying soil samples in an oven, while indirect methods use automated sensors like theta probes. Satellite images provides comprehensive coverage of the Earth's surface, and using microwave and optical remote sensing satellite images to monitor surface soil moisture regional and global level and is beneficial [41].

A. CONVENTIONAL METHODS

In-situ methods can be categorized as direct and indirect methods. Direct methods such as gravimetric [42] and volumetric [43] techniques, involve physically obtaining soil samples and analysing their moisture content through oven drying. Drilling is often necessary for these methods, which can affect the infiltration and drainage properties of the soil. In contrast, indirect methods determine moisture levels without directly removing soil samples by using automated systems that create a correlation between soil moisture and other chemical and physical soil parameters. There are two types of automated techniques: quantitative and qualitative. In addition to soil water dielectric methods like time-domain and frequency-domain reflectometry [44, 45], quantitative approaches include gamma-ray attenuation and neutron scattering [46]. Direct measurements of soil moisture content are made possible by these methods. Conversely, qualitative methods and soil-water potential devices like [47] employ resistance blocks, psychrometers [48]. These sensors monitor soil moisture at precise points on the soil layer without disturbing it. Automated soil moisture measurements are critical for determining the amount of accessible water for vegetation and crops. [49]. These in-situ approaches, however, rely on point measurements and necessitate a large number of samples to effectively characterize an area. Furthermore, determining soil moisture values in a varied soil profile might be difficult using these methods.

B. REMOTE SENSING METHODS

Over the past 20 years, improvements in remote sensing methods have been crucial in determining the moisture content of soil by tracking electromagnetic radiation reflected off the soil surface. The study of soil thermal and diurnal properties has benefited from the use of thermal infrared and microwave wavelengths. These methods measure soil moisture under a range of topographical conditions, as demonstrated by recent developments in remote sensing. The dielectric characteristics of water and dry soil have a significant impact on microwave emissivity. Remote sensing offers a comprehensive and global view of the Earth. In order to calculate soil moisture, one must first determine the emissivity using passive sensors and the dielectric constant linked to the radar backscattering coefficient intensity using active sensors. P and L bands, in

particular, have proven to be optimal for assessing soil moisture at depths ranging from 0-4 cm and 0-2 cm, respectively [2].

C. THROUGH PASSIVE AND ACTIVE REMOTE SENSING TECHNIQUES:

Passive microwave sensing was first discovered in the 1970s, that measure the soil's brightness temperature proved to be very useful [50]. Retrieving surface soil moisture from emissivity necessitates analysing the measured emissivity, which is affected by factors like surface roughness, vegetation cover, dielectric constant, and observation angle. Radiometers are sensitive to variations in soil moisture, according to previous research [51-54]. But these instruments have to cover a large area if they are to collect more energy from the relatively less microwave emissions at the surface. As a result, coarse spatial resolutions, often extending to tens of kilometres, are required.

GNSS-based soil moisture investigations are a relatively new field of study compared to active and passive microwave remote sensing. European Space Agency's Soil Moisture Ocean Monitoring (SMOS) mission [55], which launched on November 2, 2009, and NASA's Soil Moisture Active and Passive (SMAP) mission [56], which launched on January 31, 2015, have successfully recovered soil moisture data from space. However, typical satellite sensors have limitations, such as low spatial resolutions of roughly 40 km and only returning to the same location every 2-3 days. They are therefore insufficient for high-resolution uses like drought monitoring or precision farming. Overcoming these limits necessitates the development of novel methods that enable high-resolution soil moisture monitoring for a variety of applications. The ability to obtain soil moisture data using GNSS-R techniques has been proven by recent field trials. [57]. The L-band, which operates at wavelengths of 15-30 cm or 1-2 GHz, is transparent enough to identify land surface conditions and treat them as if they were bare soil [6]. These signals can pass through clouds and plants due to their longer wavelengths. As a result, radar remote sensing has emerged as a critical technology for monitoring soil moisture, enabling reliable and repeatable observations across wide regions. Recently, there have been significant advancements in the global monitoring of soil moisture through satellite radar remote sensing [58].

V. SOIL MOISTURE RETRIEVAL FROM GNSS

The permittivity of the reflecting surface significantly affects received power in bistatic GNSS-R radar, primarily through the Fresnel reflection coefficient. GNSS L-band signals, which are sensitive to the top 1-2 cm of the soil, are specifically impacted by the permittivity of the soil, which is determined by moisture content and vegetation cover. At GNSS ground-based stations, surface multipath interference from GNSS signals is used to track the ground dielectric permittivity. Techniques to control the impacts of surface roughness in soil moisture retrievals have been proposed, with the goal of minimizing interference and

enhancing dielectric permittivity measurement accuracy [22].

Passive radiometers and active radars are commonly used for remote sensing soil moisture in airborne and space missions. Radiometers measure surface temperature and moisture based on emissivity, but are sensitive to surface roughness and can be affected by background temperature variations and human interference. Monostatic radars have lower sensitivity to soil moisture variations and are more complex to process, with lower time resolution [52]. The GNSS-R method can measure soil moisture at a depth of 0 to 5 cm, which is comparable to the depth range of data on soil moisture from the SMAP and SMOS datasets [59, 60]. Therefore, GNSS-R is a bi-static radar satellite remote sensing method that estimates surface characteristics from reflected GNSS signals.

Using microwaves to measure soil moisture is based on the fundamental difference in dielectric constants between water ($\epsilon \approx 80$) and dry soil ($\epsilon \approx 4$) [4]. The GNSS Reflectometry is segmented into two categories based on signal receiving methods: bistatic radar technique and the interference pattern technique. The bistatic technique records both direct and reflected signals using a dedicated Delay-Doppler mapping receiver that has two polarized antennas [61]. Conversely, the interference pattern method collects both reflected and direct signals at the same time using a typical GNSS receiver with a single antenna [62] as shown in Fig. 3.

Kavak 1998 [11] first offered insights into the impact of ground specular reflections on L-band satellite communications and introduced a reliable method to measure permittivity, which can be utilized to determine soil moisture using GPS signals. A strong relationship between received waveforms and soil moisture levels was found by Zavorotny and Voronovich [25]. To extract soil moisture content Rodriguez-Alvarez et al. [57] designed a SMIGOL reflectometer system using the Interference Pattern Technique (IPT). Furthermore, by examining GPS multipath data, GPS receivers which are frequently employed in geodesy and geophysics are applied in soil and vegetation investigations [63]. In addition, theoretical analyses of vegetation biomass or the polarization properties of GNSS-R reflected signals are conducted using microwave scattering models. Many studies have used bistatic radar equations and inversion models for dielectric constant and soil moisture estimation [8], [9], [64 - 67]. Table 2 provides a summary of several soil moisture retrieval studies conducted previously.

Fig. 3. GNSS system; a) Single Antenna, b) Dual Antenna (after [9])

A. SNR METHOD FROM MULTIPATH

This method uses a single antenna for receiving both RHCP and LHCP and it is also called as GNSS interferometric reflectometry (GNSS-IR). Larson et al. [68] proved that the multipath signal amplitude and phase correlate well with soil moisture predictions. Chew et al. [69] used electrodynamic single-scattering forward model, showed phase and signal-to-noise (SNR) from interferograms has stronger correlation with surface soil moisture. Roussel et al. [70] developed interference pattern technique to estimate soil moisture using SNR data, showing an angle-dependent relationship and improved temporal resolution. Further, [71-74] presented algorithms to estimate near-surface soil moisture fluctuations around GPS antennas, considering vegetation's impact on SNR metrics and removing vegetation effects. However, GNSS-IR signals interpretation can be complex due to the need to separate modulation terms from SNR data, potentially increasing computational complexity. It may also be susceptible to vegetation interference, affecting soil moisture estimation accuracy. Additionally, reliance on ancillary data could limit its application in areas lacking comprehensive datasets.

Multipath interference happens when an electromagnetic signal is reflected from an object or surface and reaches an antenna indirectly. This disrupts GPS data as the tracking loop locks onto a combined signal. It is difficult to detach multipath effects in GPS carrier phase observables due to orbit, atmospheric delay, clock, and position modeling. SNR data, however, can

offer another technique for calculating multipath effects. The following simple model of GPS signal tracking is used to describe the SNR (eq. 8) at any given time [18, 69, 73]:

$$SNR = A \cos\left(\frac{4\pi H_0}{\lambda} \sin E + \varphi\right) \quad (8)$$

In this case, the reflector height is H_0 , wavelength is λ and elevation angle is E . The SNR metrics' amplitude and phase are denoted by A and φ . Zavorotny et al. [73] provided an algorithm for retrieving soil moisture specifically for bare soil conditions.

B. INTERFERENCE PATTERN TECHNIQUE

The interference pattern approach has been used by Rodriguez-Alvarez [73] to get terrestrial geophysical parameters. When soils are covered in vegetation, IPT measures the interference between direct and reflected signals, allowing surface topography, vegetation height, and soil moisture to be retrieved. In order to verify the theoretical findings, the authors in [75] created Soil Moisture Interference-pattern from GNSS Observations using L-band SMIGOL reflectometer. The IPT has been used successfully for three different retrievals: surface topography [76], vegetation height [77], and soil moisture assessment for both bare soil and vegetation-covered areas [75, 78]. Nonetheless, surface topography correction required an estimation based on a lower-resolution digital elevation model.

Table 2. Soil Moisture retrieval conducted studies

Year	Authors	Contributions	Data	Limitations
1998	Kavak et al. [22]	Investigated fading due to specular ground reflections at L-band to find ground conductivity and relative permittivity.	GPS signals under clear LOS conditions.	Neglect of surface roughness and the need for further validation to ensure reliability and applicability across different scenarios.
2000	Masters et al. [79]	The proof-of-concept results were presented on the correlation between soil moisture levels and reflected signals using GPS bistatic scatterometry.	Reflected power measurements from a modified delay mapping GPS receiver, recorded on both precipitation and dry days.	Limited by the small number of aircraft flights and the potential variability in soil moisture and ground cover.
2000	Zavorotny & Voronovich [80]	In rather challenging terrain, the impact of surface roughness is lessened when signals are received at orthogonal polarizations, improving the dependability of soil moisture retrieval.	Bistatic L-band GPS systems for remote sensing of soil moisture.	Dependence on theoretical models and simulations, without thorough validation, restricts its relevance and applicability to practical soil moisture sensing applications.
2003	Zavorotny et al. [81]	A significant correlation was showed between reflected signals and rainy conditions, suggesting that high-gain antennas enhance receiver capabilities by reducing interference.	Used GPS data to analyse waveform correlation amplitudes to study relationship between the moisture content and the reflected power.	Assumption of soil moisture homogeneity, requiring more accurate modelling of soil moisture depth profiles to align with measured data.
2004	Masters et al. [82]	Showed sensitivity to soil moisture changes after precipitation through daily soil moisture maps, and examined temporal changes.	Reflected SNR data from SMEX02 campaign from various flight days.	Constrained by requirements for refining the correlation between GPS power and soil moisture, calibrating with direct signal measurements.

Year	Authors	Contributions	Data	Limitations
2006	Katzberg et al. [83]	Successfully showed potential use of reflected GPS signals for regional soil moisture observations through calibration methods for GPS reflectivity.	SMEX2 GPS data	Need for more research into sensing depth and surface reflection phenomena considering potential vegetation attenuation effects.
2008	Larson et al. [84]	Suggested the possibility of near-real-time soil moisture estimation using a potential global network of GPS receivers.	GPS multipath amplitude variation data and Precipitation records.	Lack of calibration with in situ data and consideration of factors such as vegetation and soil type on GPS multipath amplitudes.
2009	Rodriguez-Alvarez et al. [85]	Developed Interference Pattern Technique for determining soil moisture using data from SMIGOL Reflectometer.	GPS interference signal power variations.	Drawback is its concentration on bare soil conditions, potentially limiting its applicability to real-world settings.
2010	Zavorotny et al. [86]	Revealed distinct behaviours in modulation amplitude and phase with elevation angles and moisture levels.	Measurements of GPS signal modulation patterns, reflection coefficients, antenna gain patterns.	Focuses on bare soil and does not account for factors like vegetation or surface topography, which influences signal coherence and scattering.
2011	Rodriguez-Alvarez et al. [87]	Retrieved land geophysical parameters like topography, soil moisture, and vegetation height accurately monitoring changes vegetation height and soil moisture variations.	Measurements from the SMIGOL-Reflectometer instrument.	Its focus on specific types of vegetation and topography, potentially limiting its applicability to other environments.
2012	Song et al. [88]	Analysed the correlation power peak ratio of reflected and direct signals to retrieve soil moisture values.	Data from a GNSS-R remote sensing experiment conducted at the weather services test base China.	It experienced fluctuations due to transient water reflections, and needs filtering methods to correct these fluctuations.
2013	Pierdicca et al. [89]	Addressed the potential of GNSS-R polarimetric measurements at both LHCP and RHCP polarizations.	Designed a GNSS-R instrument and developed a simulator to model the cross correlation process between reflected and direct signals.	Uncertainties due to antenna characteristics and ground truth data, sensitivity of moisture retrieval to soil roughness
2014	Pei et al. [90]	Estimated the relative permittivity of the terrain surface using the SNRs, which contributed to a better understanding of soil properties.	LHCP signals to generate and evaluate DDMs SNR time series	The study suggests that permittivity values may be underestimated in uncertain water saturation areas, urging for a more comprehensive analysis considering surface roughness.
2014	Egido et al. [91]	Found a strong correlation between reflectivity polarization ratio and soil moisture in moderately vegetated fields with surface roughness below 3 cm.	Flights captured GNSS-R polarimetric observations	Despite accurate processing and analysis of GNSS-R data, there may still be inherent uncertainties in the algorithms and interpretation methods used.
2015	Jia et al. [92]	Showed good correlation between retrieved soil moisture and underlying terrain types using GPS satellites power reflectivity	GNSS signals were processed to obtain DDMs, estimated SNR.	The duration of data collection is limited due to memory constraints, potentially limiting the coverage area or duration of measurements.
2016	Jia et al. [93]	Explored the use of the power ratio of left-hand reflected SNR over direct right-hand SNR to estimate soil surface characteristics.	Doppler maps, waveforms, and SNR time series	Need for more extensive validation studies in various environmental conditions.
2016	Roussel et al. [70]	Investigated the correlation between SNR metrics and soil moisture at different satellite elevation angles considering temporal changes and combined GPS and GLONASS data.	GPS and GLONASS SNR data at different elevation angles (low: < 30°, high: 30-70°).	While GPS and GLONASS constellations are used in the study, their coverage may differ depending on the location. Adding more GNSS constellations could strengthen the resilience of the approach.
2017	Ban et al. [94]	Developed methodologies for soil moisture estimation using BeiDou geostationary earth orbit satellites in GNSS-R	Used direct and reflected signals, analysed DDMs, and developed empirical models.	Factors such as residual moisture content, observation time intervals, and signal strength changes caused uncertainties in soil moisture.

Year	Authors	Contributions	Data	Limitations
2018	Zhang et al. [95]	Used GNSS-IR for estimating surface soil moisture and studied the effect of antenna height and vegetation .	L2C and L5 SNR data, to derive a wetness index and estimate soil moisture.	The findings are primarily based on grassland observations, and their applicability to other vegetation types may require further investigation.
2019	Jia et al. [96]	Applied the ML algorithm XGBoost to evaluate the impact of input parameter uncertainties on soil moisture retrieval results.	Utilized both simulated data sets and ground-truth dataset obtained from GNSS-R ground-based campaigns.	Suggests further exploration of alternative machine learning methods for GNSS-R data analysis.
2020	Jia et al. [97]	Compared ML methods with traditional electromagnetic models commonly used in GNSS-R for SMC retrieval.	Data from ground-based and airborne experiments were used to train ML regression models.	Accurately representing diverse soil compositions is a challenge, which impacts the performance of GNSS-R and ML models.
2021	Munoz-Martin et al. [98]	Examined the influence of surface roughness and vegetation attenuation on signals on GNSS-R signals at L1 and L5 bands using artificial neural network.	GNSS data ground-truth data, Sentinel-2 NDVI data, and ECMWF Land Surface Temperature.	There is necessity of careful algorithm design and parameter selection and accounting for the trade-off between radiometric and spatial resolution.
2022	Wang et al. [99]	Assessed the performance of QZSS signals in estimating soil moisture	Ground-based dual-antenna was used to QZSS signal data.	Further research is needed to know the impact of antenna gain, vegetation, and crosstalk on direct and reflected signals using long-term data series.
2022	Roberts et al. [100]	Estimated soil moisture by using deep learning techniques like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) to enhance global soil moisture estimates.	Measurements of CYGNSS DDMs were used as the primary dataset, and SMAP soil moisture values as targets.	The CNN showed strong correlation with SMAP soil moisture values. However, it had limitations due to soil porosity and dense vegetation.
2023	Ha et al. [101], [102]	Enhanced soil moisture estimation accuracy in dry to very dry sandy soils, thereby optimizing water allocation for agriculture, especially in Dahra, Senegal, affected by drought.	GNSS data from GPS and GLONASS satellites, data from soil moisture stations and temperature sensors were used.	To evaluate the suggested method's generalizability, more research could examine how well it works in various soil and environmental conditions.
2024	Perez-Portero, Adrian, et al. [102]	This paper demonstrates a proof-of-concept integration of GNSS-R with L-band SAR missions to enhance temporal resolution for soil moisture monitoring and future satellite synergy.	SMAP radar backscatter, SMAP GNSS-R (forward scattering) measurements.	The study is limited by short and sparse SMAP/SMAP-R datasets with coarse spatial-temporal aggregation (~36 km, monthly scale) and vegetation-related constraints
2025	Liu et al. [103]	The study introduces three-frequency GNSS-IR methods that estimate soil moisture using multipath errors from pseudo-range and carrier phase, eliminating the need for SNR-based approaches.	The study uses GNSS observations, three-frequency pseudo-range and carrier phase.	The methods may amplify noise due to linear combinations of three-frequency signals, depend on optimal satellite selection, and require careful tuning of multipath sequence length and training data split for stable results.
2026	Liang et al. [104]	The study proposes an hourly soil moisture retrieval method using multi-system GNSS-IR (GPS + GLONASS) by correcting inter-orbit phase bias.	The study uses GPS L1/L2 and GLONASS G1/G2, soil moisture data from PBO	Reference orbit selection and phase bias correction methods are not fully optimized, requiring further validation in multi-site and long-term studies.

C. DUAL ANTENNA GNSS REFLECTOMETRY GEOMETRY

The GNSS-R employing dual antennas can be described as a bistatic radar approach utilizing signals of opportunity. This method transmits signals from a satellite to the Earth's surface, where they scatter and are picked up by a GNSS receiver. Various platforms, including ground-based, airborne, and satellite, present different levels of spatial and temporal resolutions. Ground-based setups yield high-resolution data, airborne platforms offer moderate spatial resolution and regional coverage, while satellite platforms

ensure global coverage with spatial resolutions dependent on surface scattering characteristics [10].

With two antennas in each receiver, one receives direct signals and another receives reflected signals, the GNSS-R functions similarly to a bistatic radar system when operating. [105]. This system works well when the receiver and transmitter are placed in distinct locations. This allows scattered signals to come from different geometrical configurations as long as the target scatters sufficiently in the direction of the receiver. In a typical bistatic design, the transmitter and receiver are situated above the surface,

where scattering occurs mostly around a specular reflection point within the surrounding area, as shown in Fig. 4.

The zenith antenna collects the direct signal to process location data, while the nadir antenna captures the reflected signal for remote sensing of the land surface. Following specular scattering, the incoming right-hand circularly polarized (RHCP) signal converts predominantly into left-hand circular polarization (LHCP). As per Snell's Law, a specular point denotes the reflection point where the incident and reflected angles are equivalent. Encircling the specular point lies a limited area recognized as the first Fresnel zone, encompassing the strong coherent scattering component. Assuming the surface is absolutely flat, the reflected power stays coherent inside a certain active region that is known as Fresnel zone. The dimensions of the Fresnel ellipse can be estimated when there is a discernible difference between the distance from the surface to the transmitter and the receiver (or vice versa) [20]:

Fig. 4. GNSS-R Geometry (after [106])

Surface roughness causes a glittering zone near the specular point, which causes scattering called as diffuse or incoherent component, is the power that is distributed randomly in all directions. The magnitude of this scattering component is lesser than the coherent component. In this reflectometer, the LHCP signal is correlated with a local copy of the sent signal to create what are called waveforms, which are time-domain correlations for zero Doppler [78].

WAVEFORM OR DDM CORRELATION

The goal of the GNSS-R soil moisture retrieval model is to study the relation between the soil's permittivity, reflection coefficient, and soil moisture content. Many studies have focused on obtaining information about soil moisture from the microwave frequency spectrum's dielectric constant. In this field, a number of well-established theoretical and empirical models such as those proposed by Wang [3], Mironov [107], Hallikainen [108], and Dobson have been developed and are generally accepted. It is important to know and provide the percentage of clay and sand in the soil as input for these models. The Topp model (1980) [60], relates soil moisture and relative permittivity as a third-order polynomial function, functions autonomously without relying on any specific input data.

Zavorotny and Voronovich [24] employed a scattering model to compute GPS ocean reflections. Their aim was to

derive the correlation power of the sea surface waveforms. They expanded their approach to include the remote sensing of soil moisture [25]. They suggested that GPS scattering signals could offer promising prospects for soil moisture remote sensing from aerial platforms such as aircraft and satellites. They highlighted that the signal peak of reflection is linked to soil moisture, while the signal tail is influenced by surface roughness.

The scattering points on a surface create an ellipse, allowing signals to arrive at the receiver simultaneously at specific delays. Doppler frequencies are caused by the relative motion of the transmitter and receiver, generating fluctuations in the signal's carrier frequency. To determine signal intensity, the grid network generated by the crossing of iso-delay and iso-Doppler lines is used. A delay map is created by correlating a sequence of code phases with the central Doppler frequency and plotting the correlation power with the code delay. It builds a DDM by taking into account both sequences of Code delays and Doppler frequencies. These DDMs are considered fundamental and highly valuable data collected by a GNSS-R receiver [109].

SCATTERING MODELS

An incident wave experiences partial scattering in all directions and partial reflection in the specular direction when it meets with a rough surface boundary. The dispersed wave is known as the diffuse or incoherent scattering component, whereas the reflected wave in the specular direction is called the coherent component. Coherent and incoherent components both contribute to the bistatic scattering during the GNSS-R dual antenna configuration process of retrieving soil moisture, with the measured total scattered power given by eq. 9.

$$P_{pq}^r = P_{pq}^c + P_{pq}^i \quad (9)$$

In this case, the incident and scattered polarizations are denoted by p and q, respectively, while the coherent and incoherent powers are indicated by P_{pq}^c and P_{pq}^i . For cases where the surfaces are smooth and level, the incoherent power is small. For the coherent component on a smooth surface, the bistatic radar equation is given by eq. 10 [110].

$$P_{lr}^c = \Gamma_{lr} \frac{P_t G_t G_r \lambda^2}{(4\pi)^2 (R_t + R_r)^2} \quad (10)$$

Where Γ_{lr} represents reflected signal (LHCP) which is inverted from direct signal (RHCP). The transmitted signal power is represented by P_t , the wavelength is indicated by λ , and the antenna gains are represented by G_t and G_r , respectively. Then incoherent component is written by eq. 11. Eq. 11 is described by [24]:

$$P_{lr}^i = \sigma_{lr} \frac{P_t G_t G_r \lambda^2}{(4\pi)^3 R_t^2 R_r^2} \quad (11)$$

Where σ_{lr} is the Bistatic radar cross section in m^2 . Changes in θ have an effect on the coherent component, which is the

dominating factor in received power on flat surfaces. Nevertheless, specular reflection decreases and incoherent scattering increases in areas with rugged terrain and thick vegetation [111, 112]. For flat surface, the Kirchoff Approximation expressing reflectivity $\Gamma_{lr}(\theta) = |\mathfrak{R}_{lr}(\theta)|^2 e^{-h \cos^2 \theta}$ is simplified to eq. 12.

$$\Gamma_{lr}(\theta) = |\mathfrak{R}_{lr}(\theta)|^2 \quad (12)$$

Where h is roughness number and it is 0 for specular points. In terms of left- and right-hand circular polarization, the Fresnel reflection coefficient, $|\mathfrak{R}_{lr}|$ can be written as eq. 13.

$$\mathfrak{R}_{lr} = \frac{1}{2} (\mathfrak{R}_{vv} - \mathfrak{R}_{hh}) \quad (13)$$

In this case, are the Fresnel reflection coefficients [24] \mathfrak{R}_{hh} and \mathfrak{R}_{vv} are horizontal polarization and vertical polarization. These coefficients depend on the incident angle θ and the relative permittivity ϵ_r of the soil and are given in eq. 14 and eq. 15.

$$\mathfrak{R}_{hh}(\theta) = \frac{\cos \theta - \sqrt{\epsilon_r - \sin^2 \theta}}{\cos \theta + \sqrt{\epsilon_r - \sin^2 \theta}} \quad (14)$$

$$\mathfrak{R}_{vv}(\theta) = \frac{\epsilon_r \cos \theta - \sqrt{\epsilon_r - \sin^2 \theta}}{\epsilon_r \cos \theta + \sqrt{\epsilon_r - \sin^2 \theta}} \quad (15)$$

DIELECTRIC MIXING MODELS FOR BISTATIC RADAR

SNR of peak power of reflected signal [64] LHCP can be written as combining (1), (2) and (3) equations. It will yield the following equation (eq. 16).

$$\begin{aligned} SNR_{peak}^{refl} &= \frac{P_{lr}^{coh} G_D}{P_N} \\ &= \frac{1}{4} \frac{P_t G_t G_r \lambda^2 G_D}{(4\pi^2)(R_t + R_r)^2 P_N} (\mathfrak{R}_{vv} - \mathfrak{R}_{hh})^2 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Here, P_N stands for noise power and G_D for the gain of processing that of the GPS C/A code's de-spread. For the peak power of the RHCP signal, the SNR is given by eq. 17.

$$SNR_{peak}^{dir} = \frac{P_t G_t G_r \lambda^2 G_D}{(4\pi^2)(R_d)^2 P_N} \quad (17)$$

However, the ratio of SNR for the LHCP and RHCP signals can be incorporated into the calibration power shown by eq. 18.

$$\frac{SNR_{peak}^{refl}}{SNR_{peak}^{dir}} = \frac{R_d^2}{4(R_t + R_r)^2} (\mathfrak{R}_{vv} - \mathfrak{R}_{hh})^2 C_{cal} \quad (18)$$

This calibration parameter can be determined if reference data of water surface are available. Therefore, the soil moisture can be determined by employing an empirical model as shown by eq. 19. More details can be referred from [108]:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon &= (a_0 + aS + a_2C) \\ &\quad + (b_0 + b_1S + b_2C)m_v \\ &\quad + (c_0 + c_1S + c_2C)m_v^2 \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

The percentages of sand (S) and clay (C) components in soil texture.

Soil's dielectric properties are influenced by its moisture content, which affects soil reflectivity. The relative amplitudes of the direct and reflected GNSS signals can be used to measure this. Roughness of the soil surface is one of the other characteristics that can influence the measurement. Surface roughness reduces surface reflectivity exponentially, resulting in diffuse scattering components.

VI. SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

GNSS-R has displayed remarkable advantages compared to traditional microwave sensors when it comes to estimating Soil Moisture Content. This method uses two approaches to capture direct and reflected signals: (a) dual antennas and (b) single antennas with linear polarization and conventional receivers. The former often uses a dielectric approach, which converts the dielectric constant into soil moisture using existing dielectric mixing models. On the other hand, the latter approach utilizes either the interference pattern technique or the SNR amplitude to estimate soil moisture. Operating within the L band, GNSS-R benefits from superior penetration through atmospheric layers, vegetation, and even during rainy conditions. While the coherent component has traditionally been thought to be more important in land-based GNSS-R applications, new research has showed that both the coherent and incoherent components are sensitive to variations dependent on relative altitude. Furthermore, GNSS-R observations over land surfaces are significantly impacted by surface slopes, which also affect scattering behaviours.

In [113] Masters et al. for the first time made an attempt to correlate soil moisture with peak power of reflected GPS signals. The SMEX02 GPS bistatic radar experiment in [114] utilized an aircraft at 1100 feet with satellites at 65° to 85° elevation angles, estimating a scattering surface of ~ 1 km and a first fresnel zone of ~ 20 m, showed good sensitivity to soil moisture changes. At lower levels of moisture SNR data do not show significant sensitivity to the measured soil moisture [115]. SNR data may offer a different approach to multipath effect quantification [68]. In [116] SNR approach yielded soil moisture with a strong consistency, ranging from 0.9 to 0.76, while there was noticeable disagreement, especially when the soil moisture content was less than 0.1 cm³ cm⁻³. When direct and reflected waves are received simultaneously and

coherently at the antenna, where their interference occurs, they combine to form interference pattern [78]. In [57] Rodriguez-Alvarez et al. used interference pattern technique with a SMIGOL reflectometer to accurately measure soil moisture across different vegetation heights, aligning with ground truth data under different conditions. High surface roughness, exceeding 3 cm, caused incoherent scattering, limiting the accuracy of coherent scattering components and affecting the reliability of soil moisture estimation [117]. The optimal time intervals for both coherent and non-coherent processing depend on the scattered signal's coherence time, which is affected by receiver dynamics [110]. Typically, 1 ms coherent time and aggregating 100–1000 non-coherent sums are used in GPS-reflectometry applications [118, 119]. An antenna elevated 1.70 meters above the reflective surface causes specular reflection points beyond 3.5 meters, with scattering mostly occurring within the first Fresnel zone for angles exceeding 2 degrees [70]. Soil moisture content is correlated with the top of the DDM; however, resolution problems can make it difficult to determine the peak power point corresponding to a given Doppler frequency and code delay [120, 121]. Ground static receivers and the GNSS-R technique can lessen this challenge. The DDM can be smoothed using 1-D interpolation, enabling more precise peak power placement and value calculations [122]. In [123] the study found that SNR was the most significant input variable in GNSS-R, contributing between 40% and 70% to determining permittivity and soil moisture content across different soil types. Variable θ had the least importance, often below 10% and approaching zero sensitivity, indicating minimal influence on these measurements. ML techniques can reveal complex correlations and predict soil types, especially in unknown or heterogeneous soil environments. For GNSS-R soil moisture content (SMC) retrieval problems, ML regression approaches are useful as a practical substitute for relying exclusively on explicit answers obtained from physical models [124]. In [125] reveals that extending incoherent integration time reduces error standard deviation, but terrain variations necessitate NDVI correction, while reducing averaging improves resolution but increases error standard deviation. The precision of soil moisture can be influenced by factors like crosstalk, surface roughness, and vegetation. In [67], the influence of surface roughness was lessened by using longer incoherent additions and high-elevation satellites to lessen crosstalk on bare soil. Advancements in AI/ML have made CNNs more appealing for processing DDMs in GNSS-R applications. Domain experts often interpret DDM structures to identify specific reflection occurrences, leading to the development of a CNN for surface parameter targeting [126]. GNSS networks and increasing satellite numbers enable free GNSS-R tool application, improving spatiotemporal monitoring of Earth and understanding drought variability in climate change context [127]. The provided collection of studies and findings in the domain of GNSS reflectometry for soil moisture retrieval reveals several key insights. There are still issues, though, like how to lessen the effect of vegetation and surface roughness on precise

soil moisture estimation. Additionally, factors like integrating incoherent time, satellite elevation angles, and signal processing techniques influence the precision of soil moisture estimations using GNSS-R.

VII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the significant potential of GNSS-R technology in estimating soil moisture content. GNSS-R offers a solution for addressing the limitations of traditional soil moisture measurement techniques by utilizing reflected signals from GNSS satellites. Its capacity for remote sensing, global coverage, and varied platform applications (ground-based, airborne, space-borne) signifies a substantial advancement in soil moisture estimation. The exploration of GNSS-R principles, provides insights into the complexities and advantages of each approach. However, interpreting signals from single antenna receiver can be complex due to modulation terms and SNR data separation, and may be susceptible to vegetation interference and reliance on ancillary data. By analyzing bistatic radar equations and the interactions of reflected signals with the Earth's surface, this study highlights the potential for accurate soil moisture retrieval. Enhancement of estimation accuracy can be achieved through the incorporation of machine learning algorithms, calibration parameters, and empirical models into GNSS-R retrieval techniques [128]. Additionally, advancements in GNSS technology with the inclusion of multiple satellite constellations further enhance the capabilities of GNSS-R for soil moisture estimation. Despite its potential, challenges persist in utilizing GNSS-R for high-resolution soil moisture monitoring. Further research and technological advancements in this domain will continue to expand the practical applications and accuracy of GNSS-R in soil moisture estimation. Issues related to signal-to-noise ratios, incidence angles, surface roughness, and vegetation interference need further exploration. It has significant implications for agriculture, water resource management, disaster risk mitigation, and climate studies. The integration of GNSS-R technology with innovative approaches offers substantial potential for addressing critical environmental challenges and advancing our understanding of soil moisture dynamics on a global scale. Overall, GNSS-R technology stands as a promising and versatile tool for soil moisture estimation, with implications for diverse fields such as agriculture, hydrology, climate studies, disaster management, and ecological monitoring.

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